

A FINITE ELEMENT FORMING MODEL FOR BI-AXIAL FABRICS CONSIDERING MATERIAL BENDING STIFFNESS

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ABSTRACT

A macroscale finite element (FE) forming model was developed to capture the effect of fabric wrinkling, by incorporating the effects of bending stiffness. The fibre-orientation dependency for bending stiffness was addressed using a non-orthogonal constitutive framework previously developed for tracking fibre orientations of bi-axial fabric materials. A method was developed to calculate the variation of bending stiffness with curvature along the fibre direction. The bending behaviour of a non-crimp fabric (NCF) with pillar stitches was characterised by a cantilever bend test, providing input data for the material model. Simulations were performed to replicate the bias-extension behaviour of the NCF material, showing good agreement with experimental data. Wrinkles were initiated within the central area of the specimen where pure shear was assumed, at an extension of 7.5mm. Once stitches started to fail, the amplitude of the wrinkle decreased due to the release of constraints. Results indicate that the stitch-imposed constraints significantly affect the formation of out-of-plane wrinkling defects in NCF. This suggests that the critical shear angle (locking angle) can be used as a criterion for the evaluation of macro wrinkling defects, and also implies that the local removal of stitches could be a potential way to eliminate forming-induced wrinkling defects for NCF.

1 INTRODUCTION

Volume production of composite structures incorporating biaxial fabrics requires a preforming step to convert flat 2D plies into complex 3D shapes prior to liquid moulding. Manufacturing defects in the form of fabric wrinkles or fibre bridging significantly compromise the stiffness and strength [1] of fibre reinforced components made from preforms. Buckling of individual plies within the laminate is triggered locally by compressive stresses resulting from the restriction of inter-ply sliding, as the required shear deformation of adjacent plies is quite different if their initial orientations are non-identical. Fabric bridging, which is found to be the dominant defect in diaphragm forming, usually occurs over concave regions of the tool, where the fabric is locally tensioned whilst being constrained by inter-ply friction. Both the shear compliance and the bending property of fabrics are of great relevance to the formation of forming-induced wrinkles: the out-of-plane wrinkling takes place when adjacent yarns lock up as the result of excessive shear deformation [2], whilst the magnitude of the bending stiffness determines the shape and number of wrinkles [3]. The mechanism of wrinkle formation is also related to the fabric architecture, for example, non-crimp fabrics with chain or pillar stitches exhibit asymmetric shear behaviour, which may result in unique wrinkling patterns compared to woven fabrics with symmetric shear resistance. Arnold et al. [4] investigated wrinkle formation during forming NCFs over a hemispherical tool, and found that the wrinkle amplitude is dependent on the fabric architecture and the blank holder force. However, the influence of intra-ply stitches on the development of out-of-plane wrinkles in NCF has not been studied.

By predicting the occurrence of critical defects, simulation approaches are widely used to inform the preform design to achieve cost savings. Fast predictions from fish-net models (also known as the kinematic approach) [1] allow preliminary defects to be identified based on the geometrically-mapped shear angle distribution or tow curvature variation over the tool. However, the outcome of forming a given fabric onto an identical tool geometry will be different when operation procedures or boundary conditions change. This implies mechanics-based forming simulations are more reliable for defect

prediction. Mesoscopic forming mechanisms such as yarn compaction, yarn laddering/sliding and fibre-stitch interaction in NCFs can be captured by mesoscale FE models, where individual yarns and contact interactions are explicitly defined. However, this type of approach demands massive computational resource, and detailed mechanical properties of the fabric constituents at the mesoscale, e.g. transverse moduli of the fibre tow and inter-tow friction, are generally too difficult to characterise by standard testing methods.

Based on a non-orthogonal constitutive model [5], fabrics are homogenised as continuum and modelled using standard elements, enabling wide applicability and savings in run time. Membrane elements were used to facilitate design optimisation [5] and to help identify in-plane defects using representative strain components [6], but consequently wrinkle prediction is limited since the bending stiffness is overlooked. Due to the relative movement of fibres, the flexural rigidity of fabrics is known to be lower than the value derived from the tensile stiffness of yarns based on classic beam/shell theory. To capture the effect of this low bending stiffness in numerical models, different values for tensile and compressive moduli were assigned to the integration points through the thickness of shell [7] or beam elements in a hybrid mesh. This method is intuitive, but is unable to independently control bending and membrane stiffnesses, and may lead to unrealistic results when the element cross-section is subjected to combined loads. More sophisticated pantographic meshes have been developed by replicating representative fabric unit cells using various combinations of structural elements [8], with the aim of comprehensively incorporating forming mechanisms into the FE model. However, the computational cost of this method is still high due to the large number of degrees of freedom (DOFs) introduced by structural elements and connectors between them. Semi-discrete shell elements [9] have previously been formulated to decouple the membrane and bending behaviours of fabrics, but these are not readily available in commercial FE codes. A rate-dependent viscoelastic bending model for fabrics has been developed using an Abaqus user defined general shell section UGENS, where the membrane and bending contributions were captured separately by membrane and shell elements that share common nodes [10]. Usually, a constant bending stiffness is used for simplification, but nonlinear bending behaviour has been observed in experimental studies for most engineering fabrics due to the friction between fibres. This direction dependency was also reported for knitted fabrics [11], which may lead to an asymmetric bending stiffness for different specimen orientations.

The objective of the current work is to combine a previously developed macroscale material model [5] with a robust element formulation available in Abaqus/Explicit to implement the effect of fabric bending. Since the bending contribution is defined by the bending rigidities measured in the principal fibre directions, the influence of fibre reorientation due to shear is addressed by updating the fibre orientations using the material constitutive relation.

Membrane and bending behaviours are independently controlled by integrating a non-orthogonal constitutive relation into the Composite Layup Toolset within Abaqus/Explicit. The performance of the proposed method is investigated by comparing predictions with reported experimental data for both a woven fabric [8] and a NCF [6]. A structured white light scanner has been employed to measure the curvature of NCF specimens (Hexcel FCIM359) during a cantilevered bend test, in order to determine the bending stiffness along the fibre directions. Tests are performed at two orientations, since this material is known to exhibit asymmetry due to the intra-ply stitch pattern [12]. The resulting bending behaviour is implemented into the proposed simulation framework to investigate the influence of the pillar stitch on wrinkle development. The model is validated by comparing the predicted wrinkle amplitude with experimental data taken from a bias extension test.

2 EXPERIMENT

A non-crimp fabric (Hexcel, FCIM359) was used in this study. Its shear resistance was determined using the picture frame shear test [6], while the bending behaviour was characterised by measuring the side profile of a fabric specimen subjected to a cantilevered bending test. An accurate representation of the specimen curvature was determined by Structured Light Scanning (SLS). In addition, the wrinkle

amplitude during bias extension testing was determined by Digital Image Correlation (DIC) for model validation.

2.1 Picture frame shear test vs. bias-extension test

The bias-extension test is performed by applying a uniaxial tensile load to a fabric ply aligned at $\pm 45^\circ$ to the loading direction. However, it is difficult to ensure uniform shear within the central region of the specimen, especially when stitches fail or wrinkling occurs. As shown in Figure 1a, the edges of the central diamond area are distorted, which are supposed to be straight under pure shear. The established pure shear condition in the bias-extension test is interrupted by local stitch failure, which initiated at an applied extension of $\sim 22\text{mm}$. In contrast, the picture frame shear test is able to produce uniform shearing across the entire specimen area. As shown in Figure 1b, the pure shear condition is maintained within the 4-bar linkage system, even though stitches have failed. Therefore, the picture frame shear test was chosen to characterise the shear behaviour of NCF fabrics, to provide the input parameters to the simulation.

Figure 1: (a) Bias extension test (b) Picture frame test

2.2 Bending stiffness characterisation

The experiment approach for bending stiffness characterisation was based on a cantilever test, in which the fabric specimen was cantilevered by gravity. To avoid parallax error during the cantilevered bend test, a HP SLS scanner was employed to acquire a 3D point cloud of the deformed specimen, ensuring a high precision up to 0.05% of the scan size. As shown in Figure 2a, the scanner was positioned in front of the cantilevered fabric specimen and scanning commenced when the deflection of the specimen became stationary. Since twist may occur in the overhang of the specimen, points within the central strip of the point cloud (i.e. the yellow strip in Figure 2b) were projected onto the corresponding cutting plane (i.e. the plane represented by the dashed lines in Figure 2b). The width of the yellow strip in Figure 2b was chosen to be 5% of the specimen width. Six specimens with a 30 mm width were tested in two configurations to account for the asymmetric architecture. The 0° fibres were positioned on both the uppermost surface and the lowermost surface about the mid-plane. The deflection curve was obtained by fitting the projected points from six specimens using a 6th order polynomial function.

Figure 2: Bending stiffness characterisation using structured white light scanning.

The bending moment M and the curvature κ at an arbitrary point $X(x(s), y(s))$ on the deflection curve were calculated as

$$M = \int_s^L \overrightarrow{XP} \times \overrightarrow{w} du \quad (1)$$

$$\kappa = \frac{x'y'' - y'x''}{(x'^2 + y'^2)^{3/2}} \quad (2)$$

where, s is the curvilinear abscissa of Point X , L is the length of overhang, \overrightarrow{w} is the vector of the gravitational force per unit length of the fabric specimen; u is the Frenet's coordinate of Point P moving along the segment between Point X and the tip of overhang E . The relation between M and κ was fitted using Voce's model [13] with the root mean square error (RMSE) calculated to be less than 5% of the experimental data:

$$M(\kappa) = R_0 \cdot \kappa + R_\infty [1 - \exp(-\kappa/\kappa_{lim})] \quad (3)$$

where, R_0 and R_∞ are fitting constants, κ_{lim} is the exponential saturation parameter. As shown in Figure 3, the obtained M - κ curve is slightly asymmetric, which indicates the dependency of the bending stiffness on the bending direction, which is a result of the meso-architecture. It is also worth noting that the bending stiffness (i.e. the slope of the M - κ curve) decreases with the increase of curvature under both positive and negative bending.

Figure 3: Bending moment versus curvature (M - κ) for FCIM359 biaxial NCF.

3 MATERIAL MODELLING

3.1 Relating bending stiffness to yarn directions

Since the membrane and bending behaviours of fabrics can be decoupled using laminate shell elements [11], Abaqus Composites Layup Toolset was employed to assemble both contributions by assigning a set of calibrated parameters. An existing non-orthogonal fabric constitutive model [6] was used to define the bending contribution from each yarn. The bending behaviour of each yarn was added to a non-orthogonal constitutive model [5], which enables the change in fibre orientation to be tracked during forming to update the bending stiffness term. The material model was implemented through a user-defined material subroutine (VUMAT) in Abaqus/Explicit [5]. Unlike the hybrid beam/truss-membrane/shell meshes in the literature, where bending stiffness is considered via elements with rotational degrees of freedom (DOFs), the current method requires less DOFs and provides mesh-independency for non-orthogonal fibres.

3.2 Decoupling membrane and bending stiffness

Since the bending stiffness of the fabric is much lower than the tensile stiffness in the fibre direction, classic beam or shell elements cannot be directly applied to model the bending behaviour. Decoupling the membrane and bending stiffness was achieved by tailoring the layer thickness and the number of integration points within the layup. A single shell element (S4R) was used for modelling each ply within the layup, but three artificial layers were defined for each element using the Abaqus Composite Layup Toolset, where two outer surface layers were used to define the bending behaviour, while the central layer was used to define the membrane behaviour. The total thickness of the element, h , was the same as the fabric thickness, and the thickness of the two surface layers were assumed to be identical. The bending moment along each fibre direction, \mathbf{M}_{fi} , acting at the shell cross-section, was calculated by integrating the moment resulting from the fibre stress $\sigma_{fi}(z)$ at the integration points over the thickness of the shell element.

$$\mathbf{M}_{fi} = \int_{-h/2}^{+h/2} \{ \sigma_{fi}(z) \cdot \bar{F}_{33}^2 \cdot z \} dz. \quad (4)$$

Due to the incompressibility of the shell element, the thickness change \bar{F}_{33} was determined by the in-plane components of the deformation gradient $\bar{F}_{ij}(i, j = 1, 2)$, i.e.

$$\bar{F}_{33} = \frac{1}{\bar{F}_{11}\bar{F}_{22} - \bar{F}_{12}\bar{F}_{21}}. \quad (5)$$

Equation (4) implies that the stresses on the shell reference surface (i.e. the mid-plane of the shell element, where $z = 0$) has no contribution to the out-of-plane bending moment (or stiffness) of the shell element. Thus, a single integration point was assigned to the central layer to eliminate its bending contribution to the laminate layup. As a result, the bending stiffness only depends on the properties of two surface layers.

Since the thickness of each fabric ply is much smaller than other dimensions, the bending behaviour of the thin-walled shell can be derived from just the fibre directions. An identical Young's modulus (i.e. E_{fi}^{surf}) was assigned to the top and bottom surface layers, thereby the bending stiffness in the i^{th} fibre direction (i.e. B_{fi} , $i=1, 2$) was obtained as

$$B_{fi} = \frac{1}{12} E_{fi}^{surf} \left[h^3 - (t^{ctral})^3 \right] \quad (6)$$

where, t^{ctral} denotes the thickness of the central layer. According to Eq. (6), the expected bending stiffness B_{fi} can be achieved by adjusting either E_{fi}^{surf} or t^{ctral} or both. However, E_{fi}^{surf} is considered to be the most practical way to control the bending stiffness B_{fi} due to their linear relationship.

Only one integration point was assigned to each surface layer to reduce the computational cost. Thus, three integration points in total were used through the thickness direction of each fabric ply, therefore eliminating the inertial moment of each layer with respect to its centroid axis. Therefore, the fibre parallel bending stiffness, B'_{fi} , can be written as

$$B'_{fi} = \frac{1}{16} E_{fi}^{surf} (h - t^{ctral})(h + t^{ctral})^2 \quad (7)$$

The nominal Young's modulus of each fabric ply long the i th yarn (i.e. E_{fi}^{lam}) was determined according to the Rule of Mixtures

$$E_{fi}^{lam} = E_{fi}^{surf} \left(\frac{h - t^{ctral}}{h} \right) + E_{ctral} \left(\frac{t^{ctral}}{h} \right) \quad (8)$$

3.3 Curvature updating

According to the Koiter-Sanders shell theory [14], in-plane strain at an integration point through the thickness of the S4R element can be determined by superposition of the membrane strain on the reference surface $\bar{\epsilon}$ and the bending strain related to the element curvature κ . Thus, the fibre strain, ϵ_{fi} , ($i=1, 2$), in the fibre coordinate system can be determined by the fibre strain on the shell reference surface (i.e. $\bar{\epsilon}_{fi}$) and the curvature of reference surface (i.e. κ_{fi}):

$$\epsilon_{fi} = \bar{\epsilon}_{fi} + \bar{F}_{33} Z_0 \kappa_{fi} \quad (9)$$

where, z_0 is the initial distance from the integration point to the mid-plane of the shell element, \bar{F}_{33} is the thickness change defined in Eq. (5).

The non-orthogonal constitutive framework is employed to determine the strain along each fibre direction at each time increment. Eq. (9) is then used to calculate the current curvature of each yarn, which relates to the bending stiffness. Thus, their relationship should be measured as material input data for updating the bending stiffness. This non-orthogonal constitutive relation was implemented in a VUMAT based on Abaqus/Explicit. However, the calculation of the bending moment and curvature in the fibre parallel systems for each element requires data from adjacent integration points in the thickness direction, which is not directly available in the VUMAT. Therefore, a user defined subroutine VEXTERNALDB was employed to access a pre-allocated external database for passing down updated element information between time increments.

3.4 Model validation

3.4.1 Cantilever bending

Cantilevered bending behaviour was simulated and then validated against experimental data, as shown in Figure 4. The predicted deflections were compared with experimental data, where the root mean square error (RMSE) is <0.5 mm for positive bending and <1.5 mm for negative bending. Also, the shape of the simulated strips after deformation fall within the corresponding error bands (i.e. the grey band in Figure 4). Only a small difference (up to 5°) in angular deflection is observed between positive and negative bending, indicating the asymmetry in bending resistance is insignificant for this particular NCF.

Figure 4: Comparison of bending deflections from six scans with FE simulations for (a) positive (b) negative bending configurations. The red line denotes the mean deflection curve from experiment data; the blue line is the simulated deflection curve; the grey bars represent error bars from six experimental specimens.

3.4.2 In-plane shearing

Both picture frame and bias-extension shear tests were simulated to investigate the performance of the developed material model for predicting fabric shear behaviour. Shear compliance curves for a woven fabric [8] and an NCF [6] were taken from the literature (see Table 1) as model inputs to predict corresponding crosshead forces. The fabric plies were modelled using Abaqus shell elements (S4R) with an edge size of $3 \text{ mm} \times 3 \text{ mm}$. As shown in Figure 5a, the normalized shear curve predicted by the current model for the woven fabric is closely superposed with the curve predicted by the discrete model by Harrison et al [8]. The simulated wrinkling onset angle ($\sim 41^\circ$) is slightly higher than the angle obtained experimentally ($\sim 39^\circ$) by Harrison et al. [8]. In Figure 5b, the predicted cross-head force for the NCF is within the range of the experiment data [6], with the RMSE less than 3% of the peak value taken from the mean experimental curve. Good agreements indicate that the proposed model is applicable for both woven fabrics and NCF in terms of shear resistance prediction.

Test	Dimension (mm)	Material	Modulus (GPa)	Bending stiffness (Nm)
Bias-extension	200×400	Woven [8]	3.0 [8]	0.0002 [8]
Picture frame shear	Frame: 145×145 Shear region: 110×110	NCF [6]	3.0	see Section 2.2

Table 1: Material properties for model input.

Figure 5: Shear force prediction against experiment data: (a) Twill-weave [8]; (b) NCF [6].

4 FORMATION OF WRINKLES IN NCF

The non-linear M - κ curve from Section 2.2 and the shear curve produced by Chen et al [6] were used as material inputs to replicate the bias-extension test for the NCF material (FCIM359). In order to reduce the computational time, the axial Young's modulus in the fibre direction was chosen to be 3 GPa and the fibre strain was limited to $<1\%$, as recommended by Harrison et al [8]. For the bias-extension simulation, one short edge of the rectangular specimen was fixed, while a 40 mm displacement was applied to the other. The NCF was modelled using quadrilateral laminate shell elements ($2\text{ mm} \times 2\text{ mm}$) with reduced integration (S4R). The areal density of the NCF (0.44 kg/m^2) was assigned to the FE model. The run time per simulation was 5.6 hours (computer specification: Intel Core i3-7100 CPU @ 3.9 GHz; 8.0 GB, 64-bit) with a step time of 5 seconds.

Figure 6: Out-of-plane wrinkling from numerical bias-extension test against DIC measurement.

Figure 7: Shear angle distribution during bias-extension test.

The out-of-plane displacements taken from DIC measurements and FE simulations at different loading stages are compared in Figure 6. The amplitude of the wrinkle waviness increases rapidly to a peak value (~ 3.6 mm) when a 14.1 mm displacement is applied to the crosshead. The maximum out-of-plane displacement varies within the range of 3.0–3.5 mm until stitches start to fail at an extension of 23.0 mm. The wrinkling patterns monitored by DIC are approximately symmetric about the central axis in the loading direction, with the greatest waviness occurring in the centre of the specimen (see Section A-A), which agrees with the FE simulations. The amplitude of the largest wrinkle taken from the simulation is compared against DIC measurements for six specimen repeats in Figure 8 (grey area represents range and black solid line represents mean). There is good agreement between the experimental and simulation data sets (RMSE=0.24 mm, which is 8% of the maximum amplitude). The shear angle distribution becomes non-uniform when wrinkling starts (see Figure 7) and the pure shear assumption in the central diamond is no longer valid (see Figure 1a). The DIC setup is unable to track the speckle pattern on the specimen once stitches start to fail and intra-ply fibre slippage occurs. The waviness amplitude also decreases due to the release of constraints, implying the local removal of intra-ply stitches could be a potential way to eliminate forming-induced wrinkling defects for NCF.

Figure 8: Deformed ply shape taken from centre of bias extension specimen

5 CONCLUSIONS

A macroscale modelling approach has been developed to study out-of-plane wrinkle formation for an NCF with pillar stitches. The following conclusions can be drawn from the results:

- The numerical model described in this paper provides a simple and effective means for addressing fibre-orientation dependency for the bending behaviour of biaxial fabrics, avoiding the complexity associated with using a coupled beam-membrane mesh and the requirement for a user-defined element.
- By comparing the shapes of the shear region in bias-extension and picture frame tests, the picture frame test was shown to be more suitable for charactering the shear compliance of pillar-stitched NCFs.
- The bending behaviour of the NCF, measured by the cantilever test, is non-linear and asymmetric for the two bending directions.
- Wrinkle waviness from bias-extension tests provided an effective way to validate the material model.
- Numerical and experimental data show that the wrinkled NCF can be flattened as a result of stitch failure, implying that local stitch removal can be a potential way to mitigate wrinkles.

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